

Initial Coin Offering (ICO) an Innovation Funding for Digitalpreneur

Hugo Prasetyo Winotoatmojo¹, Idris Gautama², Elidjen³, Meyliana⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Universitas Bina Nusantara, Jakarta, Indonesia

Email: hugo.prasetyo@binus.ac.id

Abstract

ICO (Initial Coin Offering) is a new mechanism for raising funds from the public through websites or social media by Digitalpreneur to fund blockchain-based start-ups by selling blockchain-based tokens or coins. Through ICOs has many advantages over conventional fundraisings, such as lower fundraising costs, faster fundraising times, and large amounts of funds raised. This ICO scheme is a fundraising innovation to meet funding shortfalls for current and future projects. From the research results on 49 ICOs in Indonesia, it is known that Trust, Asymmetry Information, Community Building have a positive effect on wealth creation. In contrast, duration harms wealth creation.

Keywords: *Initial Coin Offering, Digitalpreneur, Funding, Blockchain, Bitcoin.*

INTRODUCTION

E-finance and mobile technology advancements for financial institutions are spurring new ideas. e-finance, internet technology, social networking services, social media, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics were all brought together by Fintech in the wake of the global financial crisis in 2008 (Lee & Shin, 2003). Traditional financial institutions, such as banks, may find it difficult to adapt to this new business model (Alt et al., 2018). Fintech start-ups see this as an opportunity to enter the financial services business, too, not just established banks. e-commerce and financial technology are two sorts of start-ups (fintech). Fintech is widely acknowledged as a crucial innovation in the financial sector and is on the rise, thanks in part to the sharing economy, regulation, and advancements in information and communication technology (IT) (Gomber et al., 2017). FinTech firms, like banks, have a business strategy that focuses on payment and loan services, just like banks. Personal finance advising, crowdfunding, virtual currency, Big Data, and security are among the additional services they offer (e.g., cyber security) (Leong & Sung, 2018).

In 2016, it's difficult to find a large bank, a large accounting firm, a renowned software company, or a government that is not researching cryptocurrencies, publishing papers on them, or launching so-called blockchain projects. Virtual currencies, probably most notably Bitcoin, have captivated the imagination of some, instilled dread in others, and perplexed the rest of us (Vranken, 2017). Satoshi Nakamoto, the unidentified inventor of Bitcoin, created the first cryptocurrency with no intention of creating money. Satoshi stated in his late 2008 Bitcoin announcement that he built a "Peer to Peer Electronic Cash System." The objective is to build something, and many people fail to do so when it comes to digital money. We are pleased to announce the initial release of Bitcoin, a revolutionary electronic money system that makes use of a peer-to-peer network to avoid duplicate spending. It is entirely decentralized, lacking servers and centralized authority (Nakamoto, 2008).

Capital or funds are one of the obstacles in the development of a business (Bekraf, 2018). There are several options that companies can do to overcome these obstacles. Bank credit, debt securities issuance, and share issuance (Barbosa & de Pinho, 2016). Companies that choose funding options by issuing shares may be familiar with IPO or Initial Public Offering. IPO is a term that refers to the process of offering shares of a company that is for the first time or has just been sold to the public. Companies often use these three options to fund their business. However, with technology, especially in the financial sector, there are other ways to raise funds, namely ICO or Initial Coin Offering (Wiśniewska, 2018).

The way ICOs work is similar to IPOs, but ICOs are based on cryptocurrencies. There are some visible differences between ICO and IPO (Ofir & Sadeh, 2020), among them:

1. Suppose the IPO only deals with investors, on the other hand. In that case, the ICO deals with investors and parties seeking funds for new projects, which is similar to crowdfunding but has the motive of returning investment funds.
2. Generally, ICO activities are unregulated and are not tied to a country's financial institutions. So, there is no official institution like OJK that oversees its activities.
3. The ICO structure tends to be freer with a decentralized system and minimal regulation.

ICO or token sale is a process whereby a company issues digital assets in the form of cryptocurrencies and receives funding either in fiat money or other digital currencies such as bitcoins from investors by utilizing Blockchain technology or Distributed Ledger Technology (Lipusch, 2018). ICOs are a product of the advancement of the financial sector, particularly

in blockchain technology. It is important to remember that tokens and coins in cryptocurrency refer to different things, with the main difference being that coins have their blockchain. In contrast, tokens are created using an existing blockchain network (Dasaklis et al., 2019). Digital assets issued by the company are digital currencies, all of which data is protected using cryptographic methods to create an online platform whose transactions use these tokens (Benedetti & Kostovetsky, 2021). Tokens purchased by investors can usually be used to access products or services offered by the company (utility tokens) or be a sign of participation from investors for specific projects (Dasaklis et al., 2019).

The ICO was discovered by J.R Willet through the ICO Mastercoin in July 2013, to be exact, utilizing the blockchain from Bitcoin (Fish, 2019). Mastercoin, now known as OMNI, became the basic protocol of the Tether token, which is one of the most traded crypto tokens after Bitcoin. At that time, the crowdfunding was very successful, with 4740 BTC Bitcoin raised and became an inspiration for other ICOs that followed suit. Another successful company conducted an EOS ICO that raised \$4.20 billion from ICOs (ICObench, 2017), or 5 times larger than the largest IPO in Indonesia (Rahadian, 2019). It is noted that the highest fundraising was done through Indonesia's IPO, namely Adaro Energy, in 2008, amounting to \$0.84 billion.

One of the advantages of ICOs for companies is that they can remove intermediaries from the capital-raising process and create a direct relationship between the company and investors. The interests of both parties can be harmonized, and investors will get complete share ownership. This ICO method encourages progress in the technological era, especially if later many start-up companies appear, the ICO method will often be done. Through the ICO, consumers can also find out which project coins were launched. With intense competition, information about these coins must be published so that the ICO has other benefits as a promotional medium. However, there is no protection for this ICO activity, Be-emers, so many companies are still afraid and choose not to do it. On the other hand, ICOs can be detrimental to investors because there is a possibility that the money given by investors is used for things that are not clear or out of line with the proposals submitted previously so that irresponsible people can run away and disappear while carrying the money that the ICO. investors or the term have given is SCAM. Therefore, there should be transparency and clarity in explaining the funds needed for the project.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Bank Loan vs. ICO

Every business or project certainly has risks, and this risk can be an obstacle in accessing funding or capital for the business (Wi, 2020). Banks, for example, have strict assessments in distributing business loans where this assessment determines the feasibility of the debtor and the amount of credit or funds to be provided. Likewise, other funding options tend to be difficult for companies with high business risks to access, especially start-ups. Start-up is a term used to refer to companies that are new or recently started and are in development. Due to the business cycle of start-ups that are still in the early cycle, there is a tendency for start-ups to require significant initial capital to penetrate the market (Salamzadeh & Kawamorita, 2015). But in reality, it is difficult for start-ups to access funding. Banks will limit the amount of credit because it is difficult to assess the business's sustainability and credit history, which may still be minimal, so it is categorized as high-risk credit (Salamzadeh & Kawamorita, 2015). Therefore, ICOs can be a promising method of funding for start-ups. From the number of funds, ICOs open up enormous funding opportunities, for example, when compared to bank loans.

Crowdfunding vs. ICO

ICOs are often equated with crowdfunding, and there are indeed some characteristics of this form of crowdfunding that can be found in ICOs. The similarities are the relatively low cost of fundraising, the funds collected from the public or many people, and the weak role of financial intermediaries (Adhami et al., 2019). The difference between ICO and crowdfunding is that ICO does not have an intermediary and connects investors directly with the company. In contrast, crowdfunding still uses intermediaries, for example, the platform used (Lipusch, 2018). Another difference is that the average amount of funds generated from ICOs is higher than crowdfunding. In February 2018, the top 10 funds raised through crowdfunding reached \$108 million, while in the ICO, it reached \$2.6 billion (Lipusch, 2018). In addition, ICOs also provide a higher level of liquidity because tokens can be traded while crowdfunding investments are not.

Venture Capital vs. ICO

Another type of fundraising that is often compared to ICOs is venture capital. Venture capital refers to private funding made by institutional investors in an investment or project. In addition to channeling funds, venture capital also distributes information or knowledge about the industry and direction to companies, given capital that cannot be obtained from funding through ICO (OECD, 2019). Of course, from this explanation, the way venture capital works are very different from an ICO. Another difference between venture capital and ICO is the high cost of fundraising and strict regulation (Lipusch, 2018). Venture capital must be in line with the Securities Exchange Act regulations, while ICOs do not yet have regulations that apply globally.

Initial Public Offering (IPO) vs. ICO

When viewed from the meaning, ICO can be concluded that ICO is similar to IPO. IPO is the process of selling the first shares to the public. Generally, companies that conduct IPOs have been operating for a long time and have a good level of profitability. Several things distinguish ICOs from IPOs apart from the types of assets exchanged with investors. ICOs have a low level of reliability against third parties or intermediaries, while IPOs are the opposite. IPOs are very dependent on intermediaries such as investment banks, law firms, underwriters (Lipusch, 2018). In addition, from a regulatory perspective, IPOs have a stricter level of regulation because they are supervised by particular regulators such as the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), which is different from ICOs, which do not have special regulations. In addition, additional funds are easier to obtain through an ICO because it does not require approval from the previous asset holder like an IPO. ICOs also have a higher level of risk due to more asymmetric information than IPOs due to the limited information that investors can obtain (Ofir & Sadeh, 2020). In addition, an ICO can minimize the cost of obtaining funding compared to the issuance of shares that require high costs (OECD, 2019). ICOs can also increase efficiency in terms of time. The period required to prepare an ICO is only about 1-3 months faster when compared to the issuance of shares through an IPO, which generally takes 2-5 years (Schückes & Gutmann, 2021).

Peer to Peer Lending (P2P)

In addition, ICOs are also often compared to peer-to-peer lending (P2P). Peer-to-peer lending is very different from ICO. P2P creates an obligation from the company to repay the borrowed funds, whereas ICO does not. In addition, P2P does not use digital ledger technology used by ICOs. Another difference is that investments made in P2P cannot be traded like tokens from an ICO. P2P also has stricter regulations because it is supervised by a unique regulator, namely the Financial Services Authority (OJK), while ICOs do not have special regulations or regulators (Istanti et al., 2020; Zein, 2019).

ICO Process Flow

Before the ICO is carried out, there are several stages that the company must go through. First, the company must make white paper. A white paper is a document that contains a business plan such as a description of the project, project returns, project participants, and also a roadmap for the project. In addition, the white paper also contains information on tokens such as the number of tokens issued, the number of funds needed, the payment methods accepted for purchasing tokens, the percentage of tokens held by the company, the number of tokens to be used, and others (Lipusch, 2018). After that, the company must create a channel for marketing and communication with potential investors. For example, companies can create web pages or telegram groups to share crucial information such as project details to attract potential investors. The next stage is the creation of tokens. Companies can choose to create tokens from scratch or use existing token generation services. After creation, the company can determine the duration or timeframe used to raise funds and then conduct the ICO. The company can conduct an ICO where investors interested in buying tokens will send their funds in crypto or other methods mentioned in the white paper during the specified timeframe. After the ICO period, the company will calculate the number of funds collected and compare it with the targeted amount of funds. If the amount of funds does not reach the specified target or does not meet the minimum target (soft cap), the company will return the funds to investors. But if the opposite happens, the company will send tokens to investors, and the ICO will be considered a success. Figure 1 describes the flowchart of an ICO.

Asymmetry Information

Asymmetry information is the inequality of information between one investor and another and between Digitalpreneurs and investors; this causes the decision-making by investors to invest in the ICO project may change, the higher the positive information obtained, the higher the investor's intention to invest in the ICO project. One of this information can be found from the rating value given by the ICO expert (Šapkauskienė & Višinskaitė, 2020). Ratings given by ICO experts on various ICO benchmark websites show that expert ratings are a valuable tool for investors to reduce asymmetry (Roosenboom et al., 2020). The higher the rating is given by the ICO expert, the better the ICO project; as a result, the higher the investor's intention to invest in the ICO project.

Community Building

To create hype, promotion, and user base, a Digitalpreneur builds a community. Schukes' research (Schückes & Gutmann, 2021) says that in an ICO, it is necessary to build a community with various benefits such as validating from the market, creating hype, creating loyal customers. One indicator to measure the community level is the number of telegram members from the ICO project (Fish, 2018). Telegram has various advantages to support ICO projects compared to other chat messenger applications. It can accommodate up to 200,000 members, share data up to 2GB, and create 1-way channels for various information to members such as wall magazines. In building a community, a well-built community is needed, namely a community that supports the project and understands the benefits. The community can also become a bulwark if outsiders vilify the project. However, the essential benefit of a community in an ICO is that the higher the number of community members, the higher the number of investors interested in investing in the ICO.

Trust

No less important point in an ICO is trust. A well-built trust can increase investors' intention to invest in ICO projects. The indicator to measure trust is the transparency of the CEO or Founder of the ICO to open his profile to investors, which is reflected in their social media, in this case, the LinkedIn profile. The higher the number of LinkedIn followers of a CEO or Founder of an ICO, the greater the exposure to publicity, the greater the intention of investors to invest in the ICO project (Panin, 2019).

ICO Duration

ICO duration is the length of time ICO fundraising. There are no specific rules governing how long it must be held in fundraising. Fisch's research (2019) says there are ICOs completed in less than 1 day, but there are also those completed in more than 100 days.

Wealth Creation

Hitt et al. (2001) say wealth creation is at the heart of entrepreneurship and strategic management. Wealth Creation is how much wealth is obtained by the shareholders of the organization owned by him (Fisch et al., 2018; Bhaskaran et al., 2020). Wealth creation is measured based on raised funds, which is the number of funds collected during the duration of the ICO. Successful fundraising is fundraising that can achieve soft cap or challenging cap targets. Softcap is the minimum ICO funds achieved to be able to carry out 1 business plan of an ICO project, while the hard cap is the maximum ICO funds obtained to be able to carry out the entire business plan of the ICO project (Ibba et al., 2018; Cruz, 2019).

Hypothesis

From the description above, the author tries to develop several research hypotheses as follows:

- H1: There is an influence of Asymmetry Information on Wealth Creation
- H2: There is an effect of Community Building on Wealth Creation
- H3: There is an effect of Trust on Wealth Creation
- H4: There is an effect of ICO Duration on Wealth Creation.

Figure 1 ICO Flowchart

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach. Quantitative research provides a better way to identify issues and problems. Based on the method, this research is included in descriptive research in the category of causal research to see the effect of a dependent variable on the independent variable. The ICO data used are 49 ICO data in Indonesia from 2017 – 2020, excluding 4 outlier data, with sources from the icobench website (Felix & Von Eije, 2019; Burns & Moro, 2018; Spinedi et al., 2019; Tran, 2018; Arnoldus, 2019; Florysiak & Schandlbauer, 2021; Hsieh & Oppermann, 2021; Boreiko & Vidusso, 2019) telegram and LinkedIn. The data taken is the name of the ICO, the ICO rating of the ICO expert, the number of telegram members from the ICO, the number of followers from the CEO, and the number of funds collected from the ICO. Data processing using smartPLS ver 3.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of Outer Model (Measurement Model): Validity and Reliability Testing

The outer model is a measuring model that connects indicators to latent variables to evaluate the model's validity and reliability. The measurement model's design (outer model) establishes the indicator features of each latent variable, whether reflexive or formative, in accordance with the variable's operational description. The algorithm iteration process was used to acquire the measurement model parameters (convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha), as well as R2 as a predictor accuracy parameter. The outer model's design is critical in PLS for both reflecting and formative indicators. The Outer Model is used to assess the variables' validity and the reliability of the instrument.

Validity is determined in this study by examining the convergent and discriminant validity values. Convergent validity refers to the positive correlation between indicators within the same construct. Convergent validity can be determined by computing the value of each indicator's external loading factor.

Table 1. Outer Loadings Value Results

	Asymmetry Information	Community Building	ICO Duration	Trust	Wealth Creation
CEO Follower				1	
Duration			1		
Raised Fund					1
Rating	1				
Telegram		1			

Table 1 shows the loading factor value of each of the variables studied. The loading factor value obtained shows a value above 0.7 which means it meets the criteria of convergent validity.

Furthermore, validity testing is carried out based on the average variance extracted (AVE) value.

Table 2. Validity Test based on Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Asymmetry Information	1
Community Building	1
ICO Duration	1
Trust	1
Wealth Creation	1

Table 2. shows the AVE value of each variable that is greater than 0.5, which means it meets one of the criteria of convergent validity.

Furthermore, reliability testing was carried out based on Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR) values. An instrument is declared reliable if the instrument has Cronbach's alpha and composite-reliability values for each variable greater than 0.6.

Table 3 Results of Reliability Analysis

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Asymmetry Information	1	1
Community Building	1	1
ICO Duration	1	1
Trust	1	1
Wealth Creation	1	1

Table 3 above shows that Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability of each variable studied has a value greater than 0.6. So, the variables studied in this study can be declared reliable.

Then, the discriminant validity test was carried out using the Fornell-Larcker approach. Table 4 presents the results of discriminant validity testing.

Table 4 Results of Discriminant Validity Analysis

	Asymmetry Information	Community Building	ICO Duration	Trust
Asymmetry Information	1			
Community Building	0.277	1		
ICO Duration	0.259	-0.21	1	
Trust	0.146	0.489	-0.322	1
Wealth Creation	0.286	0.916	-0.248	0.468

The square root of the AVE of a latent variable is compared to the correlation value between the latent variable and other latent variables in discriminant validity testing. It is well established that the square root of the AVE for each latent variable is bigger than the correlation coefficient between the latent variable and the other latent variables. As a result, it is concluded that it satisfies the criteria for discriminant validity.

The coefficient of determination quantifies a model's predictive accuracy. The coefficient of determination quantifies the cumulative effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables; in other words, it quantifies the contribution of exogenous variables to endogenous variable prediction. Table 5 below contains the coefficient of determination.

Table 5 Results of the Coefficient of Determination (R²)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Wealth Creation	0.845	0.831

Table 6. shows the results of the coefficient of determination of 0.845, which means that the independent variables in this study can explain 84.5% of the dependent variables, and variables explain the remaining 15.5% outside of this study.

Path Coefficient Test

The path coefficient is used to determine the magnitude of the independent variable's effect or influence on the dependent variable. The bigger the path coefficient between two independent factors and the dependent variable, the greater the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

Table 6 Path Coefficient Test Values

	Asymmetry Information	Community Building	ICO Duration	Trust	Wealth Creation
Asymmetry Information					0.062
Community Building					0.881
ICO Duration					-0.079
Trust					0.003
Wealth Creation					

Figure 2. Result Wealth Creation Model for Digitalpreneur

In light of Table 6 and Figure 2, it can be concluded that the huge path coefficient value is shown by the influence of community building on wealth generation, which is 0.881, as shown in the graph. The influence of Asymmetry Information on wealth generation, with a 0.062 significance level, is the second most important influence. The effect of trust on wealth generation is demonstrated to be the tiniest at 0.003, which is the smallest of all.

It appears from the explanation of these results that there are also variables in this model that have a path coefficient with a negative number, especially the influence of ICO Duration on wealth generation, which is a variable in the model. This demonstrates that the bigger the value of the path coefficient on one independent variable on the dependent variable, the greater the strength of the effect between the independent factors on the dependent variable.

CONCLUSION

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that information asymmetry has a positive effect on wealth creation. The higher the ranking given by ICO experts, the higher the funds collected. Community building has a positive effect on wealth creation, where the more extensive the user-based telegram of the ICO project, the higher the funds raised. Trust has a significant favorable influence on wealth creation, where the higher the followers of the LinkedIn CEO, the higher the funds raised. At the same time, the duration hurts wealth creation, where the longer the duration of the ICO, the smaller the funds raised; this could be because Indonesian ICO investors want the ICO back as soon as possible so that the longer the duration of the ICO can make ICO investors in Indonesia not interested in investing in the project. The. That. In terms of contributions related to science, this research contributes to the strategic factors that Digitalpreneurs must consider in creating organizational wealth.

ICOs have several benefits for the parties involved. For business founders or Digitalpreneurs, ICO is an option or opportunity to get extensive funding. In addition, ICOs also provide funding at low costs and in a relatively short period [14]. As for the start-up industry, ICOs fill financial gaps that arise due to the barriers start-ups have to access funding. Therefore, ICOs encourage the advancement of the start-up industry by removing barriers in terms of funding. From the investor side, ICOs provide liquidity where investors can trade the tokens they get through the ICO, and also ICO investors have the opportunity to get a high initial return, i.e., if the token purchase price is lower than the initial closing price when the token is listed on a cryptocurrency exchange. Besides, ICOs also allow everyone to invest in the ICO, unlike other funding with a higher degree of exclusivity, such as venture capital.

Further research developed from this research includes the CEO's motivation to raise funds through the ICO, namely control rights. Even though investors invest their funds, the organization's control rights remain in the hands of the CEO. In addition, future research that can be done is to include environmental turbulence factors due to the impact of COVID-

19 because 92% of Indonesian ICOs were carried out before COVID-19, while 8% of Indonesian ICOs were during the pandemic.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adhami, S., Giudici, G., & Martinazzi, S. (2018). Why do businesses go crypto? An empirical analysis of initial coin offerings. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 100, 64-75.
- [2]. Alt, R., Beck, R., & Smits, M. T. (2018). FinTech and the transformation of the financial industry. *Electronic markets*, 28(3), 235-243.
- [3]. Arnoldus, T. (2019). *Ex-ante uncertainty as a determinant of Initial Coin Offering underpricing* (Master's thesis, University of Twente).
- [4]. Barbosa, L., & de Pinho, P. S. (2016). Structure of corporate funding. *Economic Bulletin and Financial Stability Report Articles and Banco de Portugal Economic Studies*.
- [5]. Bekraf. (2018). *Mapping Dan Database Startup Indonesia 2018*. Jakarta: Badan Ekonomi Kreatif.
- [6]. Benedetti, H., & Kostovetsky, L. (2021). Digital tulips? Returns to investors in initial coin offerings—*Journal of Corporate Finance*, 66, 101786.
- [7]. Bhaskaran, R. K., Ting, I. W. K., Sukumaran, S. K., & Sumod, S. D. (2020). Environmental, social and governance initiatives and wealth creation for firms: An empirical examination. *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 41(5), 710-729.
- [8]. Boreiko, D., & Vidusso, G. (2019). New blockchain intermediaries: do ICO rating websites do their job well?. *The Journal of Alternative Investments*, 21(4), 67-79.
- [9]. Burns, L., & Moro, A. (2018). What makes an ICO successful? An investigation of the role of ICO characteristics, team quality, and market sentiment. *An Investigation of the Role of ICO Characteristics, Team Quality and Market Sentiment (September 27, 2018)*.
- [10]. Cruz, D. F. B. (2019). *Initial Coin Offering (ICOs): determinants of successful Initial Coin Offering (ICOs)* (Doctoral dissertation).
- [11]. Dasaklis, T. K., Casino, F., Patsakis, C., & Douligeris, C. (2019). A framework for supply chain traceability based on blockchain tokens. In *International Conference on Business Process Management* (pp. 704-716). Springer, Cham.
- [12]. Felix, T. H., & von Eije, H. (2019). Underpricing in the cryptocurrency world: evidence from initial coin offerings. *Managerial Finance*.
- [13]. Fich, E. M., Nguyen, T., & Officer, M. (2018). Significant wealth creation in mergers and acquisitions. *Financial Management*, 47(4), 953-991.
- [14]. Fisch, C. (2019). Initial coin offerings (ICOs) to finance new ventures. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 34(1), 1-22.
- [15]. Fisch, C. (2019). Initial coin offerings (ICOs) to finance new ventures. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 34(1), 1-22.
- [16]. Florysiak, D., & Schandlbauer, A. (2021). The information content of ico white papers. Available at SSRN 3265007.
- [17]. Gomber, P., Koch, J. A., & Siering, M. (2017). Digital Finance and FinTech: current research and future research directions. *Journal of Business Economics*, 87(5), 537-580.
- [18]. Hitt, M. A., Ireland, R. D., Camp, S. M., & Sexton, D. L. (2001). Strategic entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurial strategies for wealth creation. *Strategic management journal*, 22(6-7), 479-491.
- [19]. Hsieh, H. C., & Oppermann, J. (2021). Initial coin offerings and their initial returns. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 26(1), 1-10.
- [20]. Ibba, S., Pinna, A., Lunesu, M. I., Marchesi, M., & Tonelli, R. (2018). Initial coin offerings and agile practices. *Future Internet*, 10(11), 103.
- [21]. ICObench. (2017). EOS (EOS) - ICO rating and details | ICObench. <https://icobench.com/ico/eos> (accessed Jul. 20, 2021).
- [22]. Istanti, L. N., Zen, F., & Hadi, S (2020). Strengthening Funding for Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) With the Equity Crowdfunding Model Through the Android-Based Peer-To-Peer Lending Application. *Southeast Asia J. Contemp. Business, Econ. Law*, (23), 41-45.
- [23]. Lee, I., & Shin, Y. J. (2018). Fintech: Ecosystem, business models, investment decisions, and challenges. *Business Horizons*, 61(1), 35-46.
- [24]. Leong, K., & Sung, A. (2018). FinTech (Financial Technology): what is it and how to use technologies to create business value in fintech way? *International Journal of Innovation, Management, and Technology*, 9(2), 74-78.
- [25]. Lipusch, N. (2018). Initial coin offerings—a paradigm shift in funding disruptive innovation. Available at SSRN 3148181.
- [26]. Nakamoto, S. (2008). Bitcoin P2P e-cash paper. *The Cryptography Mailing List*.
- [27]. OECD. (2019). Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs) for SME Financing. Available: <http://www.oecd.org/finance/ICOs-for-SME-Financing.pdf>.

- [28]. Ofir, M., & Sadeh, I. (2020). ICO vs. IPO: Empirical Findings, Information Asymmetry, and the Appropriate Regulatory Framework. *Vand. J. Transnat'l L.*, 53, 525.
- [29]. Panin, A. (2019). *A multiple case study on factors affecting ICO success*.
- [30]. Rahadian, A. (2019). Ini 10 Perusahaan Peraih Dana IPO Terbesar di BEI. *cnbcindonesia.com*, 2019. <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/market/20190714190236-20-84809/ini-10-erusahaan-peraih-dana-ipo-terbesar-di-bei> (accessed Dec. 09, 2020).
- [31]. Roosenboom, P., van der Kolk, T., & de Jong, A. (2020). What determines success in initial coin offerings? *Venture Capital*, 22(2), 161-183.
- [32]. Salamzadeh, A., & Kawamorita, K. H. (2015). Start-up companies: Life cycle and challenges. In *4th International conference on employment, education, and entrepreneurship (EEE), Belgrade, Serbia*.
- [33]. Šapkauskienė, A., & Višinskaitė, I. (2020). Initial Coin Offerings (ICOs): benefits, risks, and success measures. *Entrepreneurship and sustainability issues*, 7(3), 1472-1483.
- [34]. Schücker, M., & Gutmann, T. (2021). Why do start-ups pursue initial coin offerings (ICOs)? The role of economic drivers and social identity on funding choice. *Small Business Economics*, 57(2), 1027-1052.
- [35]. Spinedi, G., Rigotti, G., Canetta, L., Camoesa, L. G., & Redaelli, C. (2019, June). Guideline for enterprise to a Value Plan through Blockchain and ICO. In *2019 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE/ITMC)* (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
- [36]. Tran, D. (2018). *Master-Thesis: Initial coin offerings: domicile as one of the key determinants for success*. Available: <https://openaccess.nhh.no/nhh-xmlui/handle/11250/2585961>.
- [37]. Vranken, H. (2017). Sustainability of bitcoin and blockchains. *Current opinion in environmental sustainability*, 28, 1-9.
- [38]. Wi, K. (2020). *Business Risk Definition*. Business Risk.
- [39]. Wiśniewska, A. (2018). The initial coin offering—challenges and opportunities. *Copernican Journal of finance & accounting*, 7(2), 99-110.
- [40]. Zein, S. (2019). Tinjauan Yuridis Pengawasan Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Terhadap Aplikasi Pinjaman Dana Berbasis Elektronik (Peer to Peer Lending/Crowdfunding) di Indonesia. *Jurnal Bisnis & Akuntansi Unsuraya*, 4(2).